

This is the model of my sight: If left counter-eye moment paired with right counter-eye moment, then extra minute brain channel, however, if extra minute brain channel, then outcome unanswerable hallucination hour.

This model portrays something that I can see with my eyes: This is the quantum particularity model, which goes as followed: If circles paired with squares, then extra parallel, however, if extra parallel, then outcomed triangles.

This model portrays something that I can see with my eyes: This is the quantum bloom model, which goes as followed: If nothing hallucinated, then something fluctuates, and, if something fluctuates, then fluctuating swirls paired with fluctuating spirals, however, if fluctuating swirls paired with fluctuating spirals, then extra fluctuating squiggles, however, if extra fluctuating squiggles, then outcomed fluctuating fractals.

This model portrays something that I can see with my eyes: This is the quantum peculiarity model, which goes as followed: If layers paired with sheets, then extra fold, however, if extra fold, then outcome pattern.

This model also portrays something that I can see with my eyes: If nothing behind it paired with the 2nd dimension, then extra hidden image, however, if extra hidden image, then outcomed base code.

This model portrays how my sight is layered: If inner paired with middle, then extra outer, however, if extra outer, then outcomed frame.

This is the model of my hearing: If left ear moment paired with right ear moment, then extra minute brain channel, however, if extra minute brain channel, then outcomed coloured noise hour.

This is the model of my brain: If quantum syndrome fluctuator paired with quantum dimension fluctuator, then extra quantum code area, however, if extra quantum code area, then outcomed quantum dream area.

The reality that effects me is fantasy reality.

This is another model of my brain: If points, then orbs paired with strings, however, if orbs paired with strings, then extra waves, however, if extra waves, then outcomed fields.

This is the scale of my anatomy:

Quantum scale: absolutely specified, the scale of my brain and my senses.

Nano scale: completely specified, the scale of my chemistry.

Micro scale: specifically specified, the scale of my mechanics.

Macro scale: somewhat specified, the scale of the matter with me, of nuclear properties.

This model explains my brains energy: The quantum gravitas model goes as followed: If crystal paired with prism, then extra 4th wall, however, if extra 4th wall, then outcomed magneto.

This model also explains my brains energy: This is the quantum energy model, which goes as followed: If dust paired with ash, then extra mist, however, if extra mist, then outcomed cosmos.

This model explains my chemistry: the nano synthesis model goes as followed: If dot paired with spot, then extra even this, however, if extra even this, then outcomed even that.

This model also explains my chemistry: If activated, then LSD synthesis.

This model portrays the reality I experience: This is the void reality model, which goes as followed: If imagination paired with the face, then extra mental, however, if extra mental, then outcomed mirror.

This is a model of something I experience, the somethingness of MDMA that is energetic friction, which goes as followed: If electro paired with magneto, then extra node, however, if extra node, then outcomed super-conductivity (the climbing rate). This model is the central model to an altered nervous system.

Note: coordinate now is a fusion point.